

Integrated Photonic Sigmoid Activation Function at 10 Gbaud/s for Photonic Neural Networks

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Abstract: We experimentally demonstrate an optoelectronic assembly of a monolithic SOA/UTC-PD chip interconnected to a TIA and realizing a 10 Gbaud/s photonic sigmoid activation function with adjustable steepness slope. © 2022 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

In the recent years, deep learning models have grown rapidly and created the need for non-conventional computing architectures with neural networks (NN) that typically comprise linear matrix multiplication and nonlinear activation function (NAF) units [1]. Neuromorphic photonics have been a suitable match due to their ability to execute energy-efficient linear operations in the optical domain at speeds far beyond the capabilities of electronic NNs. Completing, however, a photonic neural layer also requires the deployment of analog photonic NAFs in order to negate the need for SerDes and digital NAF circuit implementations, typically coming with significant energy- and latency overheads [2]. Analog photonic NAF circuit implementations proposed so far have mainly targeted the transfer of well-established digital NN activations, like ReLU, PreLU and sigmoid functions, into the optoelectronic or optical domain [1],[2]. However, their analog nature has also led to new activation functions that often proved to offer improved performance compared to commonly used NN activations when utilized in photonic NN deployments. One typical example is the photonic sigmoid (PS) activation function [3], which resulted to significant performance benefits when replacing the widely adopted ReLU activation in photonic NN configuration [4]. The PS activation has been so far realized, however, either in low-speed deployments [1], or with rather bulky and fiber-pigtailed Mach Zehnder Interferometer-based all optical circuits [3], severely hindering its adoption in integrated high-speed neuromorphic photonic setups. In this paper we demonstrate an optoelectronic compact assembly that comprises a monolithic O-band InP chip featuring a semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA) and a uni-traveling-carrier-photodiode (PD) and being wire bonded to the input of a transimpedance amplifier (TIA). By recording the output waveforms from two inverse 32-level pulse sequences at 10 Gbaud/s, the transfer function of the circuit was extracted, successfully revealing a PS shape with a slope and an output value range that can be flexibly adjusted through the SOA driving and operational conditions.

2. Experimental Setup

Fig. 1(a) shows the optoelectronic receiver assembly that consists of an O-band InP chip combining monolithically a 700 μm long SOA and a $5 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ high speed UTC-PD [5], and a 4-channel TIA chip fabricated in a 55-nm SiGe-BiCMOS technology [6]. The output of the UTC-PD was wire-bonded at the input of one TIA's channel, where the differential output electrical signal can be collected by an RF probe. The III-V chip and the TIA electronic integrated circuit (EIC) are mounted on a PCB, providing biasing of the SOA and access to TIA settings via an external computer. Fig. 1(b) shows the experimental setup employed for the characterization of the circuit's transfer function.

Fig. 1: (a) Top view microscope photo of the optoelectronic SOA UTC-PD TIA assembly, the area of each component is highlighted by the dashed lines. (b) Experimental set up used for the realization of the photonic sigmoid operation.

Fig. 2: (a) normal (blue) and inverse (green) 32-level input pulse sequences. (b), (c), (d) Vout vs input pulse peak power transfer function and the logistic sigmoid fitting for (b) $I_{soa} = 60\text{mA}$ (c) $I_{soa} = 90\text{mA}$ and (d) $I_{soa} = 60\text{mA}$ and an extra CW light. The inset tables display the parameters of Eq. (1) resulting from the Sigmoid fitting.

The Laser source 1 emitting at 1310 nm with 5 dBm output power was connected to a 40 GHz bandwidth LiNbO₃ modulator (MOD) driven by a 100 GS/s DAC. A 45 GHz bandwidth RF EIC amplified and adjusted the power coming out of the DAC before being injected into the MOD. Gain control of the SOA is also enabled by injecting into the SOA a CW light coming out of Laser 2 emitting at 1312 nm. The average power of the pulsed signal launched into the assembly is 0 dBm. A circulator placed in the line routes the counter-propagating ASE noise to a power meter (PM) for optimization of optical alignment. The signal coming out of the TIA was collected via a 40 GHz bandwidth GS RF probe, connected to a DC block before captured at the RTO featuring 160 GS/s and 65 GHz bandwidth, adjusted to 33GHz for noise reduction.

3. Results and Discussion

Two 32-level 100 ps pulse width sequences were injected at the input of the SOA for a total of 64 symbols (Fig.2(a)). The “normal” starts from the lowest power level of 0 mW and rises up to 2 mW, whereas the “inverse” starts from the highest power level of 2.3 mW and goes down to 0 mW. The testing of the circuit with the two different patterns aims to verify the absence of any memory effects originating from the SOA recovery time. By comparing the pulse trains at the output of the assembly with the input signal of Fig. 2(a), the transfer function of the circuit is extracted for three distinct circuit configurations: for a SOA driving current of 60 mA (Fig. 2(b)), 90 mA (Fig.2(c)) and finally 60 mA but employing an additional co-injected 2 mW CW signal from Laser 2 (Fig. 2(d)) for accelerating the SOA recovery time. The points of Fig. 2(b)-(d) corresponding to the normal and inverse input patterns are fitted then with the logistic sigmoid that is mathematically expressed by Eq. (1):

$$f(x) = A_2 + \frac{A_1 - A_2}{1 + e^{\frac{x - x_0}{dx}}} \quad (1)$$

with A_1 , A_2 setting the lower and upper amplitude levels, x_0 being the peak power corresponding to the half width of the total amplitude swing and dx being the slope of the function. The dots for the normal and inverse pattern exhibit similar values for the same input peak power, confirming the negligible memory effect from the SOA. In all three graphs and in both patterns, the 1 mW peak power results in a 0 V output due to the dc block employed in the TIA. As such, peak powers above 1 mW correspond to positive output values, while peak powers below 1 mW yield negative output values, suggesting that the 1 mW peak power of the incoming signal acts as a biasing term where higher peak powers can be assumed to correspond to positive and lower peak powers to negative NAF inputs. The highest dx factor defining the transfer function steepness is obtained for a 90 mA SOA current with $dx = 0.119$, then for 60 mA biasing with $dx = 0.178$ and finally with the 2 mW extra CW to $dx = 0.263$. The gain of the SOA also governs the total output voltage swing that ranges between 242 mV and 290 mV depending on the SOA driving conditions. In all cases the R-square of the sigmoid fitting is higher than 98.6%, revealing a very good confidence for the chosen function. The graphs of Fig. 2 reveal an optoelectronic circuit that is capable to provide a PS transfer function with variable steepness and output value range, both defined through the interplay between the SOA driving current and an external CW signal. The high output voltage swing also is capable to directly drive the next stage of a NN.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the EC NEBULA (871658) and ALLEGRO (101092766) project.

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